

Studies on Adsorption and Desorption of Methyl Parathion on Humic Substances

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Adsorption of methyl parathion on humic acid and its cationic forms (Ca^{II} and Fe^{III}) were studied at two different temperatures. The amounts of methyl parathion adsorbed were fitted to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The partial molar free energy change, accompanying the adsorption process follow the order, $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{-humate} > \text{humic acid} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}\text{-humate}$. Adsorption in all the cases was higher at 22° than at 35° .

THE role of soil organic matter, humic substances in particular, in controlling the fate of soil applied or soil borne toxic chemicals has been elucidated¹⁻³. Parathion is reported to owe its longterm persistence in soil to sorption by soil organic matter and hydrophobic association was emphasised in such retentions. Further studies indicate the occurrence of hysteresis in desorption of parathion from soils. The present paper reports the adsorption and desorption of methyl parathion by humic acid and its cationic forms.

Experimental

The characteristics of humic acid (HA) as extracted from Bigra Pond sediment (Burdwan, West Bengal) was reported earlier⁴. The Ca^{II} - and Fe^{III} -humates were prepared by saturating the purified HA by repetitive washing with 0.1 N solutions, and dialysing followed by drying. The dried samples (30 mg) of humic acid or its salts were taken in centrifuge tubes fitted with screw-caps and shaken with methyl parathion solutions (20 ml; 81.5% by weight, Bayer India, technical grade) of varying concentrations (10–56 ppm). Preliminary study showed that 4 h of shaking at moderate rate were required to establish equilibrium. The adsorption experiments were carried out at 35 and 22° .

For desorption experiment, an aliquot of the supernatant left behind in the centrifuge tube after centrifuging for adsorption study at the appropriate temperature was replaced by an equal volume of distilled water, reequilibrated (equilibrium time 8 h) and centrifuged. The desorption step was repeated thrice for each initial concentration. Methyl parathion in the supernatant was determined by the Averell–Norris colorimetric method⁵, in which the reduction of the parathion nitro group is achieved with HCl and Zn dust. The resulting amine was diazotised and coupled with *N*-1-naph-

thylethylenediamine to produce a colour with adsorbance maximum at 560 μm .

Results and Discussion

The adsorption isotherms of methyl parathion by humic acid substances are given in Fig. 1. These could be fitted to the Freundlich isotherm of the type,

$$X = KC^{1/n}$$

where, X is the amount of methyl parathion adsorbed per g of adsorbent, C is the equilibrium concentration, and K and n are constants. Freundlich constant K is an estimate of the adsorption capacity from solutions containing unit equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate. The K values (Table 1) were dependent on the dominant cation at both the temperatures and followed the order,

The reason for the difference in adsorption capacities of the different cationic forms of humic acid probably lies in the variation of their equilibrium solution pH, being lowest (4.5 to 4.7) in case of iron humate. The low pH may enhance H-bonding for the retention of the adsorbate due to multiple sites being made available on the adsorbent surface. Formation of voids due to H-bonding which could trap hydrophobic regions of humic acid and its salts, and Van der Waal's forces between the hydrophobic portions of the adsorbate molecules and the adsorbent surfaces are also possible.

Desorption curves (Fig. 1) show that the desorption depends on the initial concentration of the adsorbate and that methyl parathion is almost irreversibly adsorbed on HA. A decrease in K value with temperature (Table 1) is indicative of the exothermic nature of adsorption of methyl parathion on humic separations, in agreement with

Fig. 1 Adsorption-desorption isotherm of (A) humic acid, (B) Ca-humate, and (C) Fe-humate: (O) adsorption, (●) desorption.

TABLE 1—CALCULATION OF K AND $1/n$ VALUES FOR HUMIC ACID AND ITS CATIONIC FORMS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

System	Temp. °C	$1/n$	K g/g
Humic acid	22	0.805 0	1 096
	35	0.854 1	826.08
Ca-humate	22	0.895 8	745.78
	35	0.929 0	574.40
Fe-humate	22	0.913 7	1 118.39
	35	0.962 5	846.44

the earlier observations⁷ on the adsorption of linuron on humic acid. An increase in temperature, in general, leads to decreased adsorption, as physical adsorption is mostly an exothermic process.

The thermodynamics of adsorption is represented by the following reaction,

Change in partial molar free energy ($\Delta\bar{F}$) of the adsorption process is given by the thermodynamic relationship⁸,

$$\Delta\bar{F} = RT \ln K_a$$

where, $K_a = C_e/C_o$ (C_e = equilibrium concentration and C_o = initial concentration of the solution), R = molar gas constant, and T = absolute temperature (K). The numerical magnitude of $\Delta\bar{F}$ can provide a measure of the driving force of the reaction. The enthalpy changes were calculated by using the Van't Hoff equation,

$$\ln \frac{K_2}{K_1} = \frac{\Delta\bar{H}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right]$$

where R is gas constant, and K_1 and K_2 are equilibrium constants at temperature T_1 and T_2 . The entropy changes were calculated from the relationship,

$$\Delta\bar{S} = (\Delta\bar{H} - \Delta\bar{F})/T$$

The partial molar thermodynamic parameters $\Delta\bar{F}$, $\Delta\bar{H}$ and $\Delta\bar{S}$ are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

	Initial concn. ppm	Equilibrium concn. (ppm)		$\Delta\bar{F}$ (cal mol ⁻¹)		$\Delta\bar{S}$ (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		$\Delta\bar{H}$ (cal mol ⁻¹) 22 - 35°
		35°	22°	35°	22°	35°	22°	
Humic acid	10	5.0	4.5	-424.2	-468	6.1	6.5	1 463.2
	20	10.5	9.5	-394.3	-436.3	5.7	6.1	1 389.9
	30	17.0	15.5	-347.6	-387	5.2	5.6	1 284.4
	40	22.5	21.0	-352.1	-377.6	4.3	4.4	945.7
	50	29.0	27.0	-333.3	-361.1	4.3	4.5	992.3
	56	32.0	29.5	-342.4	-375.7	4.8	5.1	1 140.0
Fe-humate	10	4.5	4.0	-488.6	-537	6.8	7.0	1 635.7
	20	9.5	8.5	-455.5	-501.5	6.4	6.9	1 544.6
	30	14.0	12.5	-466.4	-513.1	6.6	7.0	1 576.2
	40	18.0	16.5	-488.6	-519	5.5	5.9	1 225.2
	50	23.5	21.5	-462	-494.7	5.5	5.8	1 235.2
	56	27.75	25.0	-429.6	-472.7	6.0	6.5	1 447.6

(Table 2 contd.)

Ca-humate	10	5.75	5.0	-351.8	-406.2	7.4	7.9	1 940.9
	20	11.25	10	-344.2	-406.2	6.9	6.8	1 628.3
	30	18.0	16.5	-367.1	-350.4	5.1	5.2	1 208.8
	40	23.75	22	-363.8	-350.4	4.5	4.7	1 045.4
	50	30.0	28	-367.1	-339.8	4.8	4.8	958.1
	56	34.0	31.5	-371.5	-337.2	4.8	4.9	1 119.2

It may be seen that for the same initial concentrations of methyl parathion (C_0) used, $-\Delta\bar{F}$ decreased in the order, Fe^{III} -humate $>$ humic acid $>$ Ca^{II} -humate, which is the same as that of the adsorption capacity of the materials. The $\Delta\bar{S}$ values in all the cases decreased with the increase in initial concentration. This is attributed to the decrease in adsorption sites with the increase in adsorption. The $\Delta\bar{H}$ values (Table 2) estimated in the experiment are relatively small (1-2 kcal mol⁻¹) which is consistent with a physical type of adsorption.

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